

ISic0828

I.Sicily inscription 0828

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list of

magistrates

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8734

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---Σ]ώσιος
2. [---Δι]ογένεο[ς]
3. [---Ἀ]ρίστωνο[ς]
4. [---]Ἀμμωνίου
5. [---]τριδας Στροβίλο[υ]
6. [---]ιερων
7. [---]στρατος Σωστρά[του]
- 7a. (vac. undefined)
8. [---]ρος Σωσιπό[λιος]
9. [---]οντων
10. [---]τοῦ Νυμφο[δώρου]
11. [---][το]ῦ Ἀπολλω[νίου]
- 11a. (vac. undefined)
12. [---][N]υμφ[οδώρου]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491437

EDCS 39101978

PHI 140298

PHI 175703

Bibliography

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